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ORIGINAL RESEARCH ARTICLE

Influence of plant nutrient management on the yield performance of transplant *Aman* rice (*Oryza sativa* L.)

Md. Imran Ali, Md. Abdur Rahman Sarkar and Swapan Kumar Paul*

Department of Agronomy, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh-2202, BANGLADESH

*Corresponding author's E-mail: skpaul@bau.edu.bd

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ABSTRACT

The experiment was conducted at the Agronomy Field Laboratory, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh, Bangladesh during June to December 2016 to investigate the influence of plant nutrient management on the yield performance of transplant *Aman* rice varieties. The experiment comprised four varieties viz., BRRIdhan70, BRRIdhan71, BRRIdhan72 and BRRIdhan73 and six nutrient managements viz. poultry manure 5 t ha⁻¹, recommended dose of prilled urea, P, K, S, Zn (160, 65, 90, 70, 10 kg ha⁻¹ of urea, TSP, MoP, Gypsum and Zinc sulphate, respectively), 75% of recommended dose of prilled urea and P, K, S, Zn + poultry manure 2.5 t ha⁻¹, 50% of recommended dose of prilled urea and P, K, S, Zn + poultry manure 5 t ha⁻¹, USG 1.8 g/4 hills and P, K, S, Zn recommended dose, USG 1.8 g/4 hills and P, K, S, Zn + poultry manure 2.5 t ha⁻¹. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Number of total tillers hill⁻¹(10.25), number of effective tillers hill⁻¹(8.85), grains panicle⁻¹ (94.23), 1000-grain weight (27.81), grain yield (5.88 t ha⁻¹) and straw yield (8.83 t ha⁻¹) were found to be the highest in BRRIdhan72. Among the nutrient management, USG 1.8 g/4 hills and P, K, S, Zn + poultry manure 2.5 t ha⁻¹ exhibited its superiority to other treatments in terms of plant height (131.0 cm), number of total tillers hill⁻¹(10.67), number of effective tillers hill⁻¹ (9.13), grains panicle⁻¹ (92.71), 1000-grain weight (26.82), grain yield (6.0 t ha⁻¹) and straw yield (8.35 t ha⁻¹). The highest grain yield (6.45 t ha⁻¹) was found in BRRIdhan72 combined with USG 1.8 g/4 hills and P, K, S, Zn + poultry manure 2.5 t ha⁻¹ and the lowest grain yield (4.85 t ha⁻¹) was found in BRRIdhan71 fertilized with poultry manure 5 t ha⁻¹. From the study, it can be concluded that transplant *Aman* rice cv. BRRIdhan72 fertilized with USG 1.8 g/4 hills and P, K, S, Zn + poultry manure 2.5 t ha⁻¹ appears as the promising practice to obtain the highest grain yield.

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INTRODUCTION

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) crop is interwoven in the cultural, social and economic lives of millions of Bangladeshis and it holds the key for food and nutritional security of the country. It is consumed as the staple food and has been given the highest priority in meeting the demands of ever-increasing population in Bangladesh. It is the most important food crop and a primary food source for more than one-third of world's population (Singh and Singh, 2008). In Bangladesh, it is grown under irrigated, rainfed and deep water conditions in the three distinct seasons namely;

Aus, *Aman* and *Boro*. Among the three distinct seasons *Aman* rice covers the second largest area of 56 lac hectares with a production of 131 lac tons of rice (BBS, 2016). In the recent years, crop productivity has stagnated or decreased in spite of consumption of increased rate of chemical fertilizers (Chen *et al.*, 2011). As a result, agricultural ecosystems remain in a state of chemical nutrient saturation, leading to huge nutrient losses through leaching, runoff, volatilization, emissions, immobilization and subsequent low nutrient use efficiency (Sun *et al.*, 2012). It is high time to search for innovative practices, which can guarantee higher yields with minimal deterioration of natural

resources. Integrated nutrient management has been shown to considerably improve rice yields by minimizing nutrient losses to the environment and managing the nutrient supply, and thereby results in high nutrient use efficiency (Kumar and Yadav, 2008). Recent field experiments have demonstrated that integrated nutrient management can lead to significant increase in crop yields while substantially reducing nutrient losses (Gupta and Sharma, 2007). Strong and convincing evidence indicates that INM practice could be an innovative and environmentally friendly strategy for sustainable agriculture worldwide (Wu and Ma, 2015). Therefore, the present investigation was carried out to have a better understanding of improving nutrient management in transplant *Aman* rice for maximization of yield.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was conducted at the Agronomy Field Laboratory, Bangladesh Agricultural University (BAU), Mymensingh, during June to December 2016 to study the influence of plant nutrient management on the yield performance of transplant *Aman* rice varieties. The land was medium high with silt-loam texture having pH 5.9. The experiment comprised four varieties viz. BRRIdhan70, BRRIdhan71, BRRIdhan72 and BRRIdhan73 and six nutrient managements viz. poultry manure 5 t ha⁻¹, recommended dose of prilled urea, P, K, S, Zn (160, 65, 90, 70, 10 kg ha⁻¹ of urea, TSP, MoP, Gypsum and Zinc sulphate, respectively), 75% of recommended dose of prilled urea and P, K, S, Zn + poultry manure 2.5 t ha⁻¹, 50% of recommended dose of prilled urea and P, K, S, Zn + poultry manure 5 t ha⁻¹, USG 1.8 g/4 hills and P, K, S, Zn recommended dose, USG 1.8 g/4 hills and P, K, S, Zn + poultry manure 2.5 t ha⁻¹. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. The size of unit plot was 4.0 × 2.5 m. Poultry manure, urea, TSP, MoP, gypsum and zinc sulphate were applied at final land preparation as per treatment requirements. Urea was top dressed in three equal splits at 15, 30 and 45 days after transplanting (DAT). USG was applied at 8 DAT at the center of four hills in every alternate row. Prior to harvest, five hills plot⁻¹ were randomly selected excluding border hills and central one square meter harvest area to record data on crop characters and yield components. The crop was harvested at full maturity and threshed by pedal thresher to record the fresh weight of grain and straw. Grains were cleaned and sun dried to a moisture content of 14%. Straws were also sun dried properly. Grain and straw yields were then converted to t ha⁻¹. The recorded data were analyzed statistically using Analysis of variance and the mean differences among the treatments were adjudged by Duncan's Multiple Range Test (Gomez and Gomez, 1984).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of variety

Crop characters, yield components and yield of transplant *Aman* rice were significantly influenced by variety. BRRIdhan70 produced the tallest plant (139.9 cm) followed by BRRIdhan72

(128.0 cm) and BRRIdhan71 (122.2 cm) while the shortest one (121.8 cm) was recorded in BRRIdhan73. These differences were mostly due to the genetic variation among the varieties. These results are consistent to those of Pal et al. (2016) and Chowdhury et al. (2016) who reported variable plant height among the varieties. The highest number of total tillers hill⁻¹ (10.25), number of effective tillers hill⁻¹ (8.85) and number of non-effective tillers hill⁻¹ (1.40) were recorded in BRRIdhan72 while the lowest values were found in BRRIdhan70. The longest panicle (26.60 cm) was found in BRRIdhan73 while the shortest one (23.57 cm) was recorded in BRRIdhan71 which was at par with BRRIdhan70 and BRRIdhan72. The highest number of grains panicle⁻¹ (88.21) and 1000-grain weight (26.66 g) were found in BRRIdhan72 whereas the lowest values were recorded in BRRIdhan70. The highest grain yield (5.88 t ha⁻¹) and straw yields (6.71 t ha⁻¹) were obtained in BRRIdhan72 followed by BRRIdhan73 while the lowest values were recorded in BRRIdhan70. The variation in number of tillers hill⁻¹ as assessed might be due to varietal characters. Nuruzzaman et al. (2000) noticed that number of tillers hill⁻¹ differed among the varieties. Varietal differences regarding grain yield was reported elsewhere (Tyeb et al. 2013; Jisan et al., 2014; Pal et al., 2016). The highest harvest index (45.00%) was recorded in BRRIdhan70, which was at par with BRRIdhan71 and the lowest one in BRRIdhan72. Variety has significant influence on harvest index was also reported elsewhere (Tyeb et al., 2013; Sarkar et al., 2014 and Chowdhury et al., 2016).

Effect of nutrient management

Nutrient management significantly influenced crop characters, yield components and yield (Table 2). The application of USG 1.8 g/4 hills and P, K, S, Zn + poultry manure 2.5 t ha⁻¹ showed its superiority in terms of plant height (131.0 cm), number of total tillers hill⁻¹ (10.67), number of effective tillers hill⁻¹ (9.13) and grains panicle⁻¹ (92.71) to nutrient management while the lowest values for these parameters were found in poultry manure 5 t ha⁻¹. The highest grain yield (6.0 t ha⁻¹) and straw yield (8.35 t ha⁻¹) were obtained when the crop was fertilized with USG 1.8 g/4 hills and P, K, S, Zn + poultry manure 2.5 t ha⁻¹. Probably this treatment might have provided adequate nutrients to plants and due to absorption of more nutrients, the crop produced the highest grain yield. These results are in agreement with that of Pal et al., 2016; Biswas et al., 2016; Islam et al., 2015; Roy et al., 2015 and Sarkar et al., 2014 who found differences in yield and yield components due to levels of nutrient management. The treatment poultry manure 5 t ha⁻¹ gave the lowest values for the same parameters due to poor nutrient supply and its uptake by plant. Application of USG 1.8 g/4 hills and P, K, S, Zn + poultry manure 2.5 t ha⁻¹ improved the yield contributing characters viz. number of effective tillers hill⁻¹, number of grains panicle⁻¹ and 1000-grain weight, which ultimately resulted in the highest grain yield. The straw yield showed similar trend as that of grain yield due to nutrient management. Application of different doses of manures and fertilizers influenced the crop characters in terms of plant height and number of total tillers hill⁻¹ which resulted in differences of straw yield. The highest harvest index

(44.14%) was found in 50% of recommended dose of prilled urea and P, K, S, Zn + poultry manure 5 t ha⁻¹ while the lowest one (41.92%) was found in USG 1.8 g/4 hills and P, K, S, Zn + poultry manure 2.5 t ha⁻¹.

Effect of interaction between variety and nutrient management

Crop characters, yield components and yield were significantly influenced by the interaction between variety and nutrient management (Table 3). The highest number of total tillers hill⁻¹ (12.42), number of effective tillers hill⁻¹ (10.20), number of non-effective tillers hill⁻¹ (2.17), grain yield (6.45t ha⁻¹) and straw yield (9.57t ha⁻¹) were obtained in BRR1 dhan72 fertilized with

USG 1.8 g/4 hills and P, K, S, Zn + poultry manure 2.5 t ha⁻¹. The lowest number of total tillers hill⁻¹ (7.93) was found in BRR1 dhan70 fertilized with poultry manure 5 t ha⁻¹ while the lowest number of effective tillers hill⁻¹ (6.67), grain yield (3.5 t ha⁻¹) and straw yield (4.85 t ha⁻¹) were found in the combination of BRR1 dhan70 and poultry manure 5 t ha⁻¹. The highest harvest index (47.28%) was found in the combination of BRR1 dhan70 and 75% of recommended dose of prilled urea and P, K, S, Zn + poultry manure 2.5 t ha⁻¹ while the lowest harvest index (38.90%) was found in the combination of BRR1 dhan72 and 75% of recommended dose of prilled urea and P, K, S, Zn + poultry manure 2.5 t ha⁻¹.

Table 1. Effect of variety on crop characters, yield components and yield of transplant *Aman* rice.

Variety	Plant height (cm)	No. of total tillers hill ⁻¹	No. of effective tillers hill ⁻¹	No. of non-effective tillers hill ⁻¹	Panicle length (cm)	No. of grains panicle ⁻¹	No. of sterile spikelets panicle ⁻¹	1000 grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Harvest index (%)
BRR1 dhan70	139.9a	8.74d	7.67c	1.09b	24.74b	75.52d	20.06a	21.38c	4.84d	5.89d	45.00a
BRR1 dhan71	122.2c	9.06c	7.76c	1.29a	23.57b	79.99c	18.22b	26.27b	5.09c	6.28c	44.83a
BRR1 dhan72	128.0b	10.25a	8.85a	1.40a	24.17b	94.23a	11.61d	27.81a	5.88a	8.83a	40.08b
BRR1 dhan73	121.8c	9.7b	8.31b	1.39a	26.60a	88.21b	13.59c	26.66b	5.3b	6.71b	44.35a
Sx	1.45	0.09	0.08	0.04	0.39	0.73	0.28	0.19	0.054	0.08	0.36
Level of significance	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**
CV (%)	4.83	4.25	4.19	11.85	6.81	3.68	7.50	3.10	4.41	5.12	3.55

Table 2. Effect of nutrient management on crop characters, yield components and yield of transplant *Aman* rice.

Nutrient management	Plant height (cm)	No. of total tillers hill ⁻¹	No. of effective tillers hill ⁻¹	No. of non-effective tillers hill ⁻¹	Panicle length (cm)	No. of grains panicle ⁻¹	No. of sterile spikelets panicle ⁻¹	1000 grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Harvest index (%)
F ₀	122.3b	8.21f	7.15f	1.07c	24.14	78.12d	19.38a	24.24e	4.45f	5.76e	43.76a
F ₁	126.7ab	9.21d	8.02d	1.19c	25.29	84.02b	15.64c	25.16d	5.2d	6.8c	43.43a
F ₂	127.8a	10.12b	8.63b	1.5a	24.43	86.03b	14.59d	26.23b	5.65b	7.26b	44.12a
F ₃	129.4a	8.73e	7.58e	1.14c	24.55	80.85c	16.84b	24.95d	4.93e	6.31d	44.14a
F ₄	130.6a	9.67c	8.33c	1.33b	25.40	85.20b	15.31cd	25.79b	5.45c	7.04bc	44.02a
F ₅	131.0a	10.67a	9.13a	1.54a	24.81	92.71a	13.47e	26.82a	6.0a	8.35a	41.92b
Sx	1.78	0.12	0.09	0.04	0.481	0.898	0.342	0.228	0.07	0.10	0.446
Level of significance	**	**	**	**	NS	**	**	**	**	**	**
CV (%)	4.83	4.25	4.19	11.85	6.81	3.68	7.50	3.10	4.41	5.12	3.55

In a column, figures with same letter (s) or without letter do not differ significantly whereas figures with dissimilar letter differ significantly (as per DMRT), ** = Significant at 1% level of probability, NS = Not significant, F₀ = Poultry manure 5t ha⁻¹, F₁ = Recommended dose of prilled urea, P, K, S, Zn (100, 65, 90, 70, 10 kg ha⁻¹ of urea, TSP, MoP, Gypsum, Zinc sulphate, respectively), F₂ = 75% of recommended dose of prilled urea and P, K, S, Zn + poultry manure 2.5 t ha⁻¹, F₃ = 50% recommended dose of prilled urea and P, K, S, Zn + poultry manure 5 t ha⁻¹, F₄ = USG 1.8 g/4 hills and P, K, S, Zn recommended dose, F₅ = USG 1.8 g hill and P, K, S, Zn + poultry manure 2.5 t ha⁻¹.

Table 3. Effect of interaction between variety and nutrient management on crop characters, yield components and yield of transplant *Aman* rice.

Interaction (Variety x Nutrient management)	Plant height (cm)	No. of total tillers hill ⁻¹	No. of effective tillers hill ⁻¹	No. of non-effective tillers hill ⁻¹	Panicle length (cm)	No. of grains panicle ⁻¹	No. of sterile spikelets panicle ⁻¹	1000 grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Harvest index (%)
V ₁ ×F ₀	125.0	7.91i	6.67l	1.25efg	24.75	66.93	22.92a	20.10	3.5 j	4.85l	42.32dg
V ₁ ×F ₁	144.4	8.58 hi	7.7ghij	0.83ij	25.97	76.36	19.97bc	21.31	4.71hi	5.77gk	44.73cd
V ₁ ×F ₂	142.2	9.00fgh	7.92ghi	1.08ghi	24.42	77.31	19.03c	22.07	5.35ef	5.93hij	47.44a
V ₁ ×F ₃	142.0	8.42hi	7.25jkl	1.17gh	24.53	71.95	22.84a	20.70	4.56hi	5.52ijk	45.28bd
V ₁ ×F ₄	143.9	8.83gh	7.91fgi	0.92hij	24.13	76.50	19.58bc	21.43	5.25fg	5.86hij	47.28a
V ₁ ×F ₅	141.9	9.67def	8.33efg	1.33def	24.63	84.07	16.03e	22.67	5.59def	7.42cd	42.98def
V ₂ ×F ₀	122.5	7.93i	7.0kl	0.93hij	22.55	73.50	21.35ab	25.20	4.4 i	5.14kl	46.18ab
V ₂ ×F ₁	121.4	8.67hi	7.83hij	0.83ij	24.28	79.57	18.28cd	25.89	4.90gh	6.23fgh	44.0cde
V ₂ ×F ₂	122.6	9.83de	8.0fgh	1.75b	24.08	81.57	16.25de	26.79	5.50def	6.7ef	44.81bd
V ₂ ×F ₃	119.2	8.5 hi	7.33ijk	1.17efgh	22.75	75.68	19.52bc	25.90	4.58 hi	5.72hijk	44.47de
V ₂ ×F ₄	121.6	9.42efg	8.0fgh	1.42cde	23.78	80.99	18.15cd	26.47	5.28fg	6.30fgh	45.58abc
V ₂ ×F ₅	125.7	10.00de	8.33efg	1.67bc	24.00	88.65	15.76e	27.39	5.88bcd	7.51cd	43.92de
V ₃ ×F ₀	124.1	8.58 hi	7.66hij	0.92hij	23.13	87.52	14.38ef	25.85	5.31efg	7.74 c	40.68gh
V ₃ ×F ₁	125.9	9.92 de	8.66cde	1.25efg	23.27	91.66	11.43gh	27.44	5.93cd	8.91 b	39.94gh
V ₃ ×F ₂	126.7	11.25b	9.41 b	1.83b	23.39	94.61	10.57 h	28.77	6.00bc	9.43ab	38.90 h
V ₃ ×F ₃	129.0	9.08gh	8.41ef	0.67j	25.46	90.57	12.00gh	27.21	5.66def	8.03 c	41.70fgh
V ₃ ×F ₄	135.4	10.25cd	8.66cde	1.58bcd	26.18	94.06	10.82gh	28.47	5.95bc	9.30ab	39.03 h
V ₃ ×F ₅	126.8	12.42 a	10.20a	2.17a	23.59	106.9	10.44 h	29.12	6.453a	9.57 a	40.2fgh
V ₄ ×F ₀	117.7	8.41 hi	7.25jkl	1.17fgh	26.13	84.53	18.8 c	25.79	4.49 hi	5.30jkl	45.86abc
V ₄ ×F ₁	114.9	9.66def	7.8hij	1.83 b	27.64	88.50	12.87fg	26.01	5.26fg	6.42fgh	45.02cd
V ₄ ×F ₂	119.5	10.4cd	9.08bc	1.33def	25.82	90.64	12.5fgh	27.28	5.73bce	6.91 de	45.32cd
V ₄ ×F ₃	127.7	8.91gh	7.33ijk	1.58bcd	25.45	85.19	13.0g	25.99	4.91gh	5.97 hi	45.11cd
V ₄ ×F ₄	121.7	10.17de	8.75cd	1.42de	27.51	89.25	12.68gh	26.79	5.32efg	6.72ef	44.21de
V ₄ ×F ₅	129.4	10.58 c	9.58 b	1.00ghi	27.03	91.15	11.6gh	28.11	6.08ab	8.91 b	40.56gh
Sx	3.57	0.23	0.19	0.09	0.97	1.8	0.69	0.46	0.13	0.20	0.89
Level of sig.	NS	**	**	**	NS	NS	**	NS	*	**	**
CV (%)	4.83	4.25	4.19	11.85	6.81	3.68	7.50	3.10	4.41	5.12	3.55

In a column, figures with same letter (s) or without letter do not differ significantly whereas figures with dissimilar letter differ significantly (as per DMRT), ** = Significant at 1% level of probability, NS = Not significant, V₁ = BRR1 dhan70, V₂ = BRR1 dhan71, V₃ = BRR1 dhan73, V₄ = BRR1 dhan74, F₀ = Poultry manure 5t ha⁻¹, F₁ = Recommended dose of prilled urea, P, K, S, Zn (100, 65, 90, 70, 10 kg ha⁻¹ of urea, TSP, MoP, Gypsum, Zinc sulphate, respectively), F₂ = 75% of recommended dose of prilled urea and P, K, S, Zn + poultry manure 2.5 t ha⁻¹, F₃ = 50% recommended dose of prilled urea and P, K, S, Zn + poultry manure 5 t ha⁻¹, F₄ = USG 1.8 g/4 hills and P, K, S, Zn recommended dose, F₅ = USG 1.8 g hill and P, K, S, Zn + poultry manure 2.5 t ha⁻¹.

Conclusion

Result revealed that the highest grain yield was produced in BRR1 dhan72 compare to other tested varieties. In case of nutrient management, the highest grain yield was obtained when the crop was fertilized with USG 1.8 g/4 hills and P, K, S, Zn + poultry manure 2.5 t ha⁻¹. BRR1 dhan72 fertilized with USG 1.8 g/4 hills and P, K, S, Zn + poultry manure 2.5 t ha⁻¹ showed the best performance in respect of grain yield. It can be concluded that transplant *Aman* rice BRR1 dhan72 fertilized with USG 1.8 g/4 hills and P, K, S, Zn + poultry manure 2.5 t ha⁻¹ appeared as the promising practice in terms of grain yield.

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